

EVALUATION OF ADVANCED CRACK ARRESTER FOR FOAM CORE SANDWICH PANEL -MODE I TYPE LOADING CONDITION

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SUMMARY

The authors invented an advanced type crack arrester for foam core sandwich panels. This concept is to install material with higher stiffness into the core-core splice as the arrester. The analytical estimation and the experimental validation of the fracture toughness test were conducted in order to confirm the crack arrester effect.

Keywords: Foam core sandwich structures, Splice-type crack arrester, Crack suppression, Core-core interface, Fracture toughness test.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the interfacial crack between a surface skin and a foam core decreases the static and fatigue strength of the foam core sandwich panel. Some researchers investigated crack suppression methods for the foam core sandwich panel [1-6]. Some of them showed the ideas to suppress the interfacial crack between the surface skin and the foam core by removing the surface skin. Two concepts, a peel stopper without joint (PS) and a combined peel stopper and joint (CPJ) were presented [1-2]. These peel stoppers consisted of a front skin, a rear skin and putty applied in a V-shaped groove milled on the foam core, which was located between the front and the rear skin. In the PS concept, the front skin laminated on the putty and overlapped with the rear skin. On the other hand, the CPJ concept had a splice laminate connecting the front and the rear skin. In these concepts, the interfacial crack propagating from the front skin to the rear skin could be stopped at the joint portion by separating the front skin from the sandwich panel. Other idea was to change the crack propagation path and to localize the interfacial crack with an embedded device named a new crack stopper in the core material [3-6]. In this concept, the path of the interfacial crack was changed to the periphery of the new crack stopper from the interface between the surface skin and the foam core. These ideas were not suitable for aircraft applications considering safety, weight and cost penalties though these were interesting for transport vehicle applications other than aircrafts.

Authors already presented evaluations of the crack arrester with a semi-cylindrical configuration, that is, a basic type crack arrester analytically and experimentally [7]. While this arrester has a simple configuration, crack suppression ability is limited. An advanced type of the crack arrester is contrived to improve the crack suppression effect from that of the basic type crack arrester by connecting the upper and lower surface skins at core-core splices. These splice portions are inevitable for the large integral structures. The larger the structure become, the more splice portions are necessary. Therefore, its application to the foam core sandwich panel structures is expected to dramatically improve the damage tolerance capability of foam core sandwich panels. The authors named this device the splice-type crack arrester. In this presentation, the concept of the splice-type arrester and its evaluation through the fracture toughness tests under the mode I type loading conditions are described.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMEN

A schematic diagram of the splice-type crack arrester is shown in Fig. 1. Carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) material, which has higher stiffness than the core material, was installed as the crack arrester in the core-core splice portion slanting off the surface skin with 30° . Detailed description of the splice type arrester is shown in Fig.2. The surface skins and the crack arrester were made of Toho Tenax UT500/#135. This CFRP material was composed of 12K twill weave fabric carbon fibre and toughened epoxy resin. The core material was Rohacell WF110 PMI core. Symmetrical stacking sequence concept of the prepreg was applied to the surface skins in order to avoid the detrimental deformation during manufacturing. The release film was installed 80 mm from the edge of the specimen between the surface skin and the foam core as a crack starter.

The splice type crack arrester of four plies consisted of two plies of CFRP fabric between tapered cores and one CFRP fabric ply covering each core. Two plies of CFRP fabric between cores and two plies adjacent to the foam core had a fibre volume content of 46% and other plies had that of 56%. The resin squeezed from the plies with higher resin content could join the parts of the specimen without an adhesive. In order to avoid sharp edges of the taped core, fillers with uni-directional CFRP material were installed to the trimmed edge of cores. The size of the specimen is 300 mm (length) x 100 mm (width) x 39.2 mm (thickness).

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of splice type arrester.

Ply No.	Materials	Orientation (deg.)
P1	QU135-197A Rc=35%	± 45
P2	QU135-197A Rc=35%	0/90
P3	QU135-197A Rc=45%	0/90
P4	QU135-197A Rc=45%	± 45
P5	QU135-197A Rc=45%	± 45
P6	QU135-197A Rc=45%	0/90
P7	QU135-197A Rc=45%	0/90

Fig.2 Stacking sequence of the specimen with crack arrester.

ANALYTICAL ESTIMATION

The crack suppression effect of the splice type arrester was evaluated by comparing the energy release rates at the crack tip for the FE model with and without the crack arrester. The ABAQUS Ver.6.4.1 FEM code was used in the FE analyses. As for the FE model, surface skins, the crack arrester and the foam core of WF110 were modeled with plain strain elements. The interfacial crack was located just below the resin layer, which was squeezed from the surface skin. Mode I type loading condition is shown in Fig.3. The constant load of 100 N was applied at 30 mm from the end of the release film. The locations of the crack tip were defined as parameter L that was the distance between the crack tip and the edge of the crack arrester. The energy release rates were calculated with crack closure integrals [8] using FEM results for the crack tip locations shown in Fig. 4.

The comparison of the energy release rates at crack tip with and without the crack arrester is shown in Fig.5. Under the constant loading, the energy release rates for the FE model with crack arrester decreased as the crack tip approached the edge of the crack arrester though those for the FE model without the crack arrester increased. The similar result was obtained for estimation of the basic type crack arrester, which was the semi-cylindrical configuration of the crack arrester [7]. This decrease of the energy release rate can be explained by the load redistribution between the foam core portion near the crack tip and the crack arrester. The stress distribution of σ_{yy} is shown in Fig.6. Comparing the stress distribution at $L = 40$ mm to $L = 0$ mm, the stress near the crack tip, which was the stress singularity point, decrease while the stress distribution of the

crack arrester increased. This change of the stress field leads to the decrease of the energy release rate at the crack tip and the suppression of the crack propagation.

Fig.3 Schematic diagram of the mode I type loading condition.

Fig.4 Crack tip location for the FE analyses.

P = 100 N

Fig.5 Analytical estimation of splice type arrester.

DCB
L=40mm

DCB
L=20mm

DCB
L=5mm

DCB
L=0mm

Fig. 6 Stress distribution of σ_{yy} (Constant loading).

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

In order to evaluate the analytical results, fracture toughness test under mode I type loading was conducted. Two test specimens with the crack arrester and one without the arrester were fabricated with the autoclave and prepared for the test. The test concept in the JIS K 7086 [9] for CFRP laminate specimen was applied. A pre-crack of approximately 5 mm was introduced prior to the test. The crack tip locations were measured with a traveling microscope and orange pigment was applied to some specimen for easy visual inspection of the crack tip locations. The overview of the fracture toughness test is shown in Fig.7. Test loads were applied with the loading speed of 2.0 mm/min, considering relatively lower fracture toughness than that of the solid laminate specimen, until the initial crack propagated less than 7 mm and then the specimen was unloaded. The load-

Fig.7 Overview of the test set-up.

displacement diagram with and without this splice type crack arrester is shown in Fig.8. The test result with the arrester indicated that critical load, which was the load at the time of crack onset for each crack growth step, increased with stable crack propagation as the crack tip approached the leading edge of the arrester while the critical load for the specimen without the arrester decreased in the stick slip manner as the crack propagated. Similar results were obtained in the evaluation of the basic type crack arrester [10]. In order to evaluate the crack arrester effect quantitatively, the parameter of the apparent energy release rate was introduced. This parameter was calculated with FE model without the crack arrester using critical loads with the arrester and corresponding crack length obtained through the fracture toughness test. The apparent fracture toughness was compared with the fracture toughness derived from the fracture toughness test results without the crack arrester. This comparison is shown in Fig.9. The apparent energy release rate was found to increase to thirteen times greater than the interfacial fracture toughness without the crack arrester, which was almost constant. This increase correspond to about $\sqrt{13} = 3.6$ times increase of the critical load with the same crack length. This result provided an experimental indication of the crack suppression effect.

The failure morphology of the specimen with the arrester is shown in Fig.10. Detail of the failure portion is shown in Fig.10 (a). This picture shows that the interfacial crack propagated near the edge of the arrester and then kinked into the foam core. The crack propagation path is shown in Fig.10 (b). In the Fig.10 (b), the end of the path A and path B correspond to $L = 3.4$ mm and $L = 0.38$ mm in Fig.8, respectively. It was revealed that the interfacial crack grew along the path A to the point of $L = 3.4$ mm. Then, the crack propagated along the path B away from the interface and approximately parallel to the crack arrester. The crack stopped at the point of $L = 0.68$ mm and reached the maximum critical load. After reaching the maximum critical load, the crack was kinked into the core along the path C during the subsequent loading. This crack kinking might be occurred due to the local failure of the core material. These fracture process indicated that the splice type crack arrester completely stopped the interfacial crack near the edge of the arrester and local failure of the core material led the crack into the core

of the sandwich panel. This type of the arrester is suitable for the heavier load bearing structural elements owing to the stronger crack suppression effect while the basic type crack arrester is appropriate for the lighter load bearing member with large area considering its simple and lightweight advantages.

A study of the design criteria and effective NDI (Non-destructive inspection) method for the suppressed crack are the next subjects because these items are significant for wide spread use of the crack arrester concept.

Fig. 8 Relationship between critical load and cross-head displacement.

Fig.9 Comparison of the apparent fracture toughness.

(a) Detail of the failure portion.

(b) Crack propagation on path and failure locations.

Fig. 10 Failure morphologies of the splice type crack arrester.

CONCLUSION

The splice type crack arrester can stop the interfacial crack completely. The quantitative estimation indicates that the splice type of the crack arrester has the crack suppression effect of thirteen times comparing with the sandwich panel without the crack arrester, and this new concept is expected to enhance the damage tolerance characteristic of foam core sandwich panels.

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